

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

Replication and Sustainability Roadmap v2

Work Package 7, Deliverable D7.15

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

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List of Acronyms

CO	Citizen Observatory
CS	Citizen Science
EO	Earth Observation

Glossary

Citizen Observatory	Citizen Observatories (COs) are community-based environmental monitoring and information systems, that invite individuals to share observations, typically via mobile phone or the web. In GREENGAGE, COs oversee running CS campaigns to gain evidence for policy making. Notice that a Citizen Science (CS) Campaign comprises a period when a group of Citizen Observers with a shared mission and hypothesis gather data at different places and regularly get together to analyse together the correlation of their collected data with other external data sources to validate such hypothesis
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GREEN Engine	GREENGAGE's dedicated technological platform leveraging GREEN Infrastructure to enable GREENGAGE CO activities.
Pilot Owner	The city or authority responsible for the implementation of a particular GREENGAGE innovation pilot.

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Executive summary (publishable)

This document provides the final version for the strategy for replicating and upscaling GREENGAGE's workflows and technical framework to other cities or regions, focusing on citizen engagement and sustainability of project assets. The strategy is based on the project's achieved technical developments and the needs identified in the development and execution of GREENGAGE's 5 pilots. The document is covering all three aspects covered by the project: The social engagement, the policy change and the technical integration of GREENGAGE's Observatories. As this report is produced at the end of the GREENGAGE project, it builds on D7.14 by providing an updated overview of the replication and sustainability potential of the GREENGAGE tools by the GREENGAGE pilots. It provides several recommendations and highlights maturity of GREENGAGE tools and their potential to be replicable across other cities or communities. It also explains the continued availability of code documentation via GitHub and training via openly available repositories, combined with flexible deployment options via AIT servers will support the sustainability of GREENGAGE assets beyond the project's lifetime.

Related documents

All GREENGAGE deliverables that are related to this document are listed below, and are available at GREENGAGE website <https://www.greengage-project.eu/knowledge-base/deliverables/>.

GREENGAGE Deliverable D7.14 Replication and Sustainability Roadmap v1(Peters-Anders J. et al., 2025)

GREENGAGE Deliverable D6.8 GREENGAGE based Citizen Observatory White Book for PAs v2 et al., 2025)

1 GREENGAGE summary

The pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aimed to promote innovative governance processes, and tried to help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project leveraged citizens' participation and equipped them with innovative digital solutions that shall transform citizen's engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, the aim was to inspire citizens to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The idea was to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This was facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO). In GREENGAGE, Citizen Observatories were and are a place where pilot cities co-examine environmental issues integrating novel bottom-up processes with top-down perspectives. This provides the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems at ground level with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aimed to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS, in-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.

The Citizens Observatory campaigns were deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano Valley (Italy), Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aimed to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, as well as gathering new data which should complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: Structure of project GREENGAGE.

2 Introduction

Purpose of the Document: To depict a comprehensive strategy for replicating and upscaling GREENGAGE's workflows and technical framework to other cities or regions, focusing on citizen engagement and sustainability of project assets.

The objectives being:

- Replication of citizen-led initiatives, i.e., GREENGAGE Observatories and their workflows.
- Ensuring long-term sustainability of the project's tools, methods, and collaborations.

3 GREENGAGE's Replication and Upscaling Strategy

For GREENGAGE being a Horizon Europe project which is funded by taxpayers' money the project needs to ensure that its results and outcomes are sustainable after the end of the project's lifetime. The following chapters depict the final plan for a strategy for replication and upscaling of GREENGAGE's assets, methodologies and workflows. The goal was to define key principles and steps for expanding the project's approach to new cities wanting to set up future Observatories (replication) and ensuring an extended use by more Citizen Observers of GREENGAGE's workflows and technology within the existing pilots, Bristol (UK), Copenhagen (DK), North Brabant (NL), Turano and Gerace (IT), that is upscaling.

3.1 Establishing Sustainable Stakeholder Consortia & Communication Channels

Objective: To ensure a long-term sustainability of GREENGAGE's findings and results, the path is clear: Ensure long-term collaboration between Public Administrations, Citizen Observers, and other stakeholders. To accomplish this the following approach will be followed:

1. Formalize a Post-Project Governance Model: Create (or sustain the already established) advisory board consisting of representatives from public administrations, citizen science groups, and research institutions.
2. Set up an online community platform (currently planned: GitHub) for ongoing discussions, updates, and troubleshooting, so the communication is continuing already established channels that will continue to operate.
3. Sign Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs) between key stakeholders (e.g., municipalities, NGOs, SMEs) to ensure ongoing commitment after the lifetime of GREENGAGE.

Key Challenge & Solution

Risk	Solution
Stakeholders may lose interest after project funding ends.	Assign clear roles and responsibilities for maintaining the tools and communication channels.
Conflicting interests among stakeholders may arise, reducing the effectiveness of collaboration.	GREENGAGE has now created an inclusive stakeholder engagement plan. Further a detailed guide is provided that covers how to use or benefit from GREENGAGE experiences - a good starting point is the GREENGAGE White Book.
Lack of formalized governance could result in disorganized collaboration after the project ends.	GREENGAGE pilots are currently trying to establish a Post-Project Governance structure via knowledge exchange with the Observers and the political stakeholders to sustain the legacy of GREENGAGE. They are also informed to have trained specialists invited in future Observatories. The White Book is, again, a good starting point to learn about the governing structure including Innovation Action Board, Pilot

	Support Team and Core-Team to establish when developing future Observatories.
Resistance from local communities due to a lack of understanding or trust in the Citizen Observatory model.	GREENGAGE introduced and tested in Datathons a robust community engagement strategy that included informational workshops, transparent discussions, and the active involvement of community members offering concrete inputs to tackle the local challenges. By fostering trust through open communication and by showcasing the tangible benefits of participation, citizens were more likely to embrace GREENGAGE's Observatory model. This has especially been demonstrated in the Barton Hill Civic Observatory in Bristol pilot.

3.2 Setting Up and Designing Citizen-Led Initiatives

GREENGAGE provides guidelines for designing initiatives that are adaptable to different cities and citizens' needs. The project's assets (e.g., the GREENGAGE website, the GREENGAGE knowledge base, the GREENGAGE academy and the project's White Book) include detailed descriptions on how and where to start to establish a Citizen Observatory and which stakeholders to include. This includes best practices for identifying local topics of interest and customizing initiatives.

GREENGAGE already demonstrated this set-up and design process in its 5 pilots:

Bristol:

The Bristol Pilot focused on monitoring the East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood (EBLN) initiative, which aims to enhance the quality of life in East Bristol through a smart urban governance approach. This approach involved co-discovery and co-development phases to understand the needs of the community, identify desired changes, and uncover barriers to creating a more liveable neighbourhood. The GREENGAGE observatories focused on monitoring and evaluating the impact of planning interventions placed in the neighbourhood on trial-basis.

The sustainability of the GREENGAGE technologies and workflows is -at the time of writing- still under discussion in Bristol and will be reported in the 2nd Periodic Report in January 2026.

Key challenges & solution:

Risk	Solution
Political constraints lead to an atmosphere where Citizen Observatories are seen as a challenge in ongoing proceedings, so they are not further implemented in other activities.	GREENGAGE needed to be communicated as a clearly neutral way of gathering insights in neighbourhoods via collection of data and discussion of results. Local communities also see GREENGAGE technologies suitable for data collection activities (e.g., housing survey through GREENGAGE App), not directly related to EBLN pilot.
Funding for technical infrastructure cannot be established beyond the lifetime of the project.	Currently the project is in discussion with Bristol City Council to sustain GREENGAGE beyond the project's lifetime. As of time of writing, the neighbourhoods in Bristol will be able to use GREENGAGE's technologies via the AIT hosted servers.
Limited capacity to facilitate further experiments and missions	The project currently tries to hand over the GREEN Engine technologies to the local community organisations for sharing ownership of and running COs in the future. Local partner, UWE Bristol, plans to continue supporting local communities beyond the lifetime of the GREENGAGE project, and deliver AI

	training for qualitative data analytics and capacity building.
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Copenhagen:

As part of the continued commitment to citizen engagement and environmental stewardship, Miljøpunkt Amager (MPA) has taken important steps to ensure the long-term sustainability of the tools and workflows developed through the GREENGAGE project.

With a focus on citizen science, local data collection, and accessible technology, MPA has embraced a model that aligns with core mission and operational capacity. Recognizing the role as a local environmental hub with a small team and no in-house technical development resources, they have prioritized a strategy that centers on coordination, facilitation, and community empowerment. To this end, MPA have designated a GREENGAGE Coordinator within the team. This role serves as the primary liaison between Miljøpunkt Amager, technical partners, and the broader community, ensuring that the GREENGAGE platform and associated tools remain functional, relevant, and integrated into local activities.

In a short time perspective, the tool “Conversation Station” has been included in a successful local funding application, and the other GREENGAGE tools for data collection of mobility data have been included in another EU application (DUT).

It has been the ambition of Miljøpunkt Amager from entering into the GREENGAGE project to act as a trusted data steward for the district and collect, organize, and share environmental data—particularly on-air quality, noise and mobility patterns—generated by local residents but trusted by all stakeholders. This data is made available to municipal stakeholders and the public, supporting evidence-based decision-making and community dialogue.

To ensure the continuity of these efforts, MPA have begun supporting the local community of practice with new data sources. One is the local council’s traffic network—an informal group of engaged citizens who coordinate local voices into public hearings and municipality plans. Through the GREENGAGE tools, MPA support campaign planning, outreach, and data collection, and continue to engage citizens to equip residents with the knowledge and tools to participate meaningfully in environmental monitoring. As such the GREENGAGE activities have been embedded into events and seasonal themes to maximize visibility and participation. These activities are also reflected in funding applications and strategic priorities, ensuring that citizen science remains a sustained and supported element of our work.

In line with environmental values, MPA have taken steps to minimize the carbon footprint of operations. We prioritize digital communication, reuse equipment across campaigns, and encourage sustainable transport for all in-person events. Our commitment to low-impact operations extends to our use of technology, where we advocate for energy-efficient hosting and responsible hardware procurement through our technical partners, and for the re-use of equipment (i.e. using Tiny LLMs on Raspberry Pies for processing).

Through these actions, Miljøpunkt Amager is proud to demonstrate how a small, community-focused organization can lead the way in digital environmental engagement. By leveraging ready-to-use tools, fostering local ownership, and maintaining a clear focus on citizen participation, ensuring that the legacy of the GREENGAGE project continues to grow—empowering residents and supporting a more sustainable, data-informed future for our district.

Key Challenge & Solution:

Risk	Solution
Political constraints lead to an atmosphere where Citizen Observatories are seen as a challenge in ongoing proceedings, so they are not further implemented in other activities.	GREENGAGE was communicated as a clearly neutral way of gathering insights in neighbourhoods via collection of data and discussion of results. Ongoing town-hall meetings showing solutions to decision makers work to this end.
Funding for technical infrastructure cannot be established beyond the lifetime of the project.	Applications for local funding opportunity has been pursued. One application has been accepted that include the conversation station.

North Brabant:

Within the North Brabant Pilot there have been two Citizen Observatories; one set up from a top-down motivation and the other from a bottom-up topic. The BUAS Cycling Lab Observatory was instigated from a top-down desire to stimulate bike use in a university destination, by creating an inventory of what motivates and demotivates the use of the bike. These insights could subsequently be used to set up campaigns to facilitate more bike accessibility of the university. For this Observatory then, the establishment was determined by an institutional goal which relied on citizen data to be tailored to an organisation.

The target of the Cycling Lab Observatory was to involve (initially) employees and (later) students in the discussion around the bikeability of the campus. Through a series of surveys and workshops, participants would share their main motivations to bike, and demotivation to not do so. Repeated meetings would over time provide a statistically valid overview of (de)motivators. Key motivators were subsequently built upon in follow-up workshops, in order to facilitate taking the bike more. These follow up sessions for instance focused on the facilitation of leisurely bike route planning or gaining control of bikeability by learning bike maintenance skills. This way, the Observatory built upon citizen data to create tailor made campaigns to increase the appeal of biking in reaching the university.

The sustainability of this Observatory manifested in several events and upscaling possibilities. The actions yielded a bike competition week - rewarding a bike bell to the colleague who cycled most during the week – and organised leisure bike trips planned by different observers. Next to that, there are plans to expand the lab to students and include bike tutorials for expat students. As these are lunch meetings, the sustainability of the Observatories is dependent on the continued institutional support, next to participant interests.

The bottom-up Observatory was instigated from a citizen desire, inventoried through a member survey of the citizen panel organisation of the Fietsersbond. The topic of bike path maintenance was forwarded as something that citizens desire more attention on and demand a stronger voice in. The Provincial government subsequently outlined their maintenance protocol, as well as the protocols of participating municipalities. The first steps of this Observatory focused on expectation adjustments between government parties with objective maintenance protocols, and citizen organisations with subjective experiences of the level of maintenance of biking paths; what can citizen data add to the existing protocols and what level of analysis can governments demand from volunteers?

Citizens were tasked with scoring bike paths that were selected based on their previously objective maintenance evaluation. Next to scoring these paths on objective characteristics, observers could add explanations of their evaluation scores, adding subjective data to the mix. This was done with the help of the GREENGAGE App as well as the Fietsersbond App. This Observatory showed that citizens score the maintenance level of bike paths more optimistically than the governmental evaluations do, but that their subjective evaluations draw attention to non-maintenance elements such as traffic safety, or environmental influences (like overgrown grass). Next to this evaluation difference, the Observatory showed that subjective data can work as a calibrating foil to official evaluation procedures, and functions as a 'search light', drawing attention to prioritising dimensions in the maintenance agenda. Additionally, the data pipeline regarding maintenance would benefit from clearer data labelling on 'maintenance', 'safety', and 'environment' data.

The sustainability of this project is ensured through the result of the combination of subjective with objective data. For the provincial processes, a subjective foil was deemed considerably valuable. This data gathering process can therefore be undertaken in a similar manner around different topics than maintenance. The GREENGAGE App can play a role here, but it is dependent on the existing infrastructure around the topic. Observatories as potential way to structure citizen participation in the Netherlands, in accordance with the new Environmental Law, can therefore live a life beyond the project lifetime.

Key Challenge & Solution

Risk	Solution
Political constraints lead to an atmosphere where Citizen Observatories are seen as a challenge in ongoing proceedings, so they are not further implemented in other activities.	GREENGAGE needs to be communicated as a clearly neutral way of gathering insights in neighbourhoods via collection of data and discussion of results.
The chosen focus on cycling maintenance is not a contentious topic resulting in less intrinsic citizen motivation to engage	The focus of the Observatory was partly shifted to creating more transparency between governmental processes and citizen data. This gave it a secondary appeal to which citizens responded
The inclusion of governmental authorities in the Observatory was complicated by governmental reliance on objective data while observers gathered mostly subjective data	The contribution of subjective citizen data to objective government data became a key focus of the Observatory, looking specifically at complementary functions
The areas of data gathering were rather remote, limiting available observers	Organising events ensured that reaching locations became coordinated. Broadening the scope of observers increased chances of reaching rural locations

Turano:

The Turano pilot has established a Citizen Observatory focused on environmental monitoring, sustainable mobility, and community engagement through cultural and archaeological campaign. The success of the initiative was related the strong local interest in the archaeological campaign, combining heritage awareness with environmental and rural engagement. Local stakeholders involved include the municipality, local communities, cultural associations, and schools, who contribute to the collection of data and documentation of the archaeological sites and surrounding landscapes.

To keep engagement alive in the future, the pilot plans to establish formal agreements with local non-profit associations capable of maintaining long-term activities. For example, partnerships with organizations like Ecoinspire Lab ETS in Rome, which is successfully applying the GREENGAGE App for community-led environmental monitoring, will ensure continuous citizen participation and integration of Observatory data into local initiatives. The CO through GREENGAGE App aims to become a permanent local resource, combining digital tools and community engagement to preserve archaeological heritage while fostering sustainable rural practices. Agreements with local non-profits will secure continuity beyond the project.

Key Challenge & Solution

Risk	Solution
Funding for technical infrastructure may not be ensured beyond the project's lifetime.	Reach out to initiatives such as the IMPETUS project to receive further funding beyond the project's lifetime. Additionally, develop partnerships with local municipalities and regional authorities to ensure continuity and alignment with regional development plans.

Limited broadband connectivity may hinder data collection and engagement	Advocate for improved broadband infrastructure by collaborating with national and EU programmes. Coordinate with telecommunication providers to explore opportunities for expanding coverage in rural and underserved areas.
Community engagement in data collection and decision-making may decline over time.	Strengthen community outreach programs, focusing on raising awareness and providing training on the importance of data collection and participatory decision-making. Partner-up with local schools, universities, and community centres to engage a wider demographic.
Environmental and mobility data collection may not be fully integrated into broader regional policies.	Build relationships with regional policymakers and integrate the Citizen Observatory's data into local and regional planning processes. Promote evidence-based policy-making that incorporates insights from the Observatory, particularly in environmental management and sustainable mobility.
Demographic decline and aging population hinder the implementation of innovative solutions.	Leverage initiatives aimed at revitalizing rural communities, such as the Rural Development Program (RDP), to attract younger populations. Promote the establishment of local innovation hubs and co-working spaces that appeal to entrepreneurs and digital nomads.

Gerace:

In Gerace, the Citizen Observatory was set up with a focus on upcycling of waste and circular economy practices. Stakeholders include municipal authorities, local associations, schools, and artisans, who contribute to workshops, data collection, and co-creation activities around waste reuse and sustainable practices. To ensure sustainability, the local administration is committed to maintaining a physical hub dedicated to upcycling, complemented by the use of the GREENGAGE App for continuous community involvement. This combination of a tangible facility and digital engagement allows residents to actively participate in monitoring, reporting, and co-designing circular economy initiatives over time. The Gerace Citizen Observatory is intended to remain an ongoing, community-led initiative, supporting local policies on waste management and circular economy. The physical hub, together with the digital platform, ensures that the GREENGAGE approach continues to guide sustainable practices well beyond the project duration.

Key Challenge & Solution

Risk	Solution
Limited long-term engagement due to scarce resources and a dispersed rural population.	Establish formal agreements with local non-profits to maintain continuous activities. Integrate the GREENGAGE App with educational programmes and community workshops to reinforce participation.
Challenges in sustaining engagement in upcycling and circular economy initiatives.	Combine a permanent physical hub with ongoing digital engagement through the GREENGAGE App, supported by the local administration and active community associations.
Limited geographic coverage of observed topics may reduce the representativeness of data.	Engage regional or city-wide panels and select study sites based on accessibility and relevance rather than solely on project constraints.
Lack of political will limit continuation of the Citizen Observatory after the project ends.	Design Observatories that can operate independently of governmental support, maximising community

	ownership and ensuring tools and processes remain functional and accessible.
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3.3 Continuing Awareness Raising via Training & Experiments' Results

The deployment of GREENGAGE Observatories is as much a citizen driven initiative as it is a government pursued methodology. The training modules are not just to make citizens aware of the tools, but also for the policy makers to get an idea on how to **setup and design a CO** and use a **GREENGAGE tool**. This includes trainings on the informed and organised formulation of a data inquiry, to prevent random data gathering by citizens to which effective feedback is limited. Second to that, stakeholders from governance settings are limited by budgets, existing frameworks, and plannings, so involving citizens in a process risks creating implausible expectations. Trainings focused on realistic expectation management and attuned data inquiries and feedback can help streamline the Observatory process. Finally, **COs** are a novel form of working and it should be clear what governments take on when relying on the method of Observatories. Therefore, a showcase of best practices or other reference projects should provide clarity on the different work forms possible with a **CO**. The GREENGAGE project can provide the first of such possibilities and best practices to be shared further. In the future, a good starting point will be consulting GREENGAGE [White Book and Knowledge base](#).

Objective: Ensure knowledge transfer through web-based learning and city partnerships.

To reach this goal, GREENGAGE proposes the following activities:

- After the mandatory lifetime of GREENGAGE's website, training materials should be hosted on the pilots' web portals (if available). During the past months GREENGAGE continued to create multilingual content for:
 - e-learning modules,
 - best practice examples and
 - lessons learnt

based on Observatory results.

This included training modules for **citizens** on:

- Scientific methods and analytical techniques
- Data collection and analysis procedures

As well as training modules for **policy makers** on:

- Requirements for productive and targeted data inquiries
 - Expectation management around policy adaptation possibilities
 - References on inclusive policy making projects and possibilities
- GREENGAGE also tried contextualizing training materials by incorporating insights from the different political and social environments of the GREENGAGE pilots. In the future this can help make the training more adaptable and relevant to diverse settings. This could, e.g., consider the type of policy-making actor (e.g., non-profit association with institutional support at the national level, regional government, municipal authority or local community organisation).
 - GREENGAGE is planning to integrate with existing educational platforms, i.e., collaborate with MOOC platforms (e.g., Coursera, edX, FutureLearn) to reach a broader audience (this might only be possible in future projects that will use GREENGAGE). This collaboration will, e.g., allow for a seamless hosting of e-learning modules on the EU Citizen Science Academy (moodle.eu-citizen.science), reaching a diverse European audience already engaged in similar initiatives. GREENGAGE also established the citizen-observers.eu platform to further disseminate and create networks of Observatories to foster awareness rising.
 - GREENGAGE also plans with webinars & online workshops to periodically organize training sessions featuring real-world CO applications (to be done within future projects by the GREENGAGE partners).

- Additionally, the existing project-specific YouTube channel will continue to operate beyond the project's duration, providing access to existing video materials without further development of content.

Key Challenge & Solution

Risk	Solution
Citizens or policy makers may have unrealistic expectations regarding the impact of the GREENGAGE Observatories.	Provide realistic expectation management through targeted training that explains the scope of COs, but also by providing well-structured informal training related to the technologies that can help citizens empower themselves, including understanding the limitations and potential outcomes of data collection. This empowerment will not only enhance citizens' capacity to contribute effectively to the Observatories but also increase their confidence in using the tools and technologies involved.
Challenges in adapting the methodology to various cities or communities with different needs.	For future Observatories customize training content based on local context, incorporating best practice examples from the different pilot sites. By providing case studies that illustrate how Citizen Observatories were adapted in different settings.
Technological applications were difficult to communicate in relation to some chosen topics	Trainings need to be focused on the general and varied use of the technology, instead of solely a tutorial for one use. This way the further application became possible.

3.4 Motivating and Sustaining Citizen Engagement

Another possibility to strengthen sustainability of GREENGAGE's workflows and digital tools is to incentivize initial participation (e.g., gamification, recognition or paid community ambassadors) of Citizen Observers.

Incentivisation happens through stimulation methods as well as through topic choice. Supported by the exploration guidelines in the GREENGAGE Academy, CO organisers should carefully consider the main topic or challenge of a CO. A non-contentious topic incites only incidental observers, requiring further recruitment, engagement, and incentivisation measures. A contentious topic, like excessive trucks driving through residential streets, will incite more intrinsic motivation, requiring less engagement activities. The long-term engagement motivation of the Citizen Observers can be even further stimulated by continuous feedback loops and regular events. An important role will be taken by community leaders and ambassadors in maintaining interest in a certain topic of an Observatory (or extending it to further research questions).

NB:

A final remark regarding monetary compensation: While Citizen Observatories rely on volunteers as observers, the full integration of both the data collected and the data-gathering processes into governmental engagement, analysis, and organisational workflows often requires specialist expertise. Such expertise typically entails monetary compensation. Depending on the composition of observers and the stakeholders involved in the Observatory, some of the necessary competencies may already be available; however, this cannot be assumed for all COs. It is therefore important to address this limitation upfront and incorporate it into expectation management from the outset.

Key Challenge & Solution

Risk	Solution
Citizen Observers may lose motivation after the initial phase, leading to decreased participation and engagement.	Implement gamification techniques, such as point systems, badges, or public recognition, to continuously incentivize participation. Regularly highlight the impact of their contributions through updates or events, reinforcing the value of their involvement. Strengthen the capacity or time of data analysts to talk to citizens and observers.
Tasks demanded of observers are too complex or time consuming, so participation is hindered, or a one-off	Integrate different forms of participation, ranging from data gatherers to full data analysts, allows for different levels of involvement to each benefit from participation

3.5 Reaching a Wider Community

To reach a wider community we propose the following:

- Leveraging social media, local events, and partnerships to attract more participants.
- Collaborating with local media and influencers to amplify reach.
- Providing examples of successful outreach campaigns from the project. A good starting point will be again GREENGAGE's White Book that signposts to various GREENGAGE resources. A caveat about a wider community should be made regarding continuous dialogue and expectation management. To facilitate the acceptance and uptake of Observatory-gathered data, a clear outlining of expectations must be set up throughout the process. Policy makers cannot promise changes beforehand. Therefore, to gather a wider community while keeping the policy makers on board, the positioning of the CO as a participation experiment or as an extension of a functioning methodology should be communicated and logged at an early stage. Here continuous dialogue and expectations management are key tools to set up a fruitful CO.

Key Challenge & Solution

Risk	Solution
GREENGAGE Observatories might get less attention in the community as needed to fulfil their goals	A social media campaign needs to be thoroughly planned and constant updates on the Observatory and its doings is needed to keep people attached to the Observatory
Expectations could be too high regarding policy changes in the community	Be transparent from the very beginning and have local stakeholders and administration on board who can tell about the range of possible changes after the Observatory has concluded and found new evidence on a certain topic
Challenges in engaging a diverse, wider audience through social media, local events, or partnerships might lead to an unbalanced representation of the community, where only specific groups participate.	Ensure outreach efforts are designed to engage a broad spectrum of the community, with particular focus on underrepresented or seldom-heard voices. Use various channels to target different demographics (e.g., youth-focused events, elderly-targeted media campaigns, etc.). Use the statistical functions of Superset to monitor the bias of your Observers.
The attempt to attract a wider community could lead to unrealistic expectations regarding the impact of the data collected,	Communicate clearly from the outset that the Observatories are participatory experiments and tools for data collection, not immediate drivers of policy change.

potentially causing dissatisfaction when policy changes do not occur immediately.	Regularly update participants on the progress of the initiative, acknowledging their contributions and clarifying that the data collected will support future decision-making but not guarantee immediate changes.
The core topic or challenge of a Citizen Observatory can turn out to be too mundane or specialistic, preventing broader uptake	Flexibility in focus points during the Observatory can shift attention from the data topic to other innovative aspects of the Observatory, such as the collaboration possibilities

3.6 Feedback Integration

Feedback forms integrated into the GREENGAGE App can capture insights from municipalities and citizens, providing valuable data for iterative improvements. **To do so, the following steps will be necessary:**

- Establishing feedback mechanisms to continuously improve replication efforts.
- Incorporating insights from planned Datathons and Summer School into new city initiatives.

Key Challenge & Solution

Risk	Solution
Feedback is not specific enough to be helpful to the processes	Have feedback thoroughly planned and then depicted in the GREENGAGE surveys on the GREENGAGE App
Feedback mechanisms may not be well-utilized or may fail to capture comprehensive insights if citizens or municipalities are not motivated to participate or do not see the value in providing feedback.	Ensure that feedback collection is framed as a vital part of the decision-making and improvement process. Clearly communicate the importance of their input for the success of the initiative. Provide incentives or recognition for participation but also strengthen the informal training approach to increase the skills required to increase community resilience.

4 Sustainability of GREENGAGE's Project Assets

To maximise the long-term impact of GREENGAGE's tools, methods, and collaborations, it is essential to establish sustainable frameworks that ensure continued use and development beyond the project's official duration. This includes fostering networks, making use of open data practices, maintaining accessible tools, building new features for emerging needs of new end users (e.g., Cities) and ensuring active stakeholder engagement.

For sustaining GREENGAGE project assets, we propose the following:

- Create an Overview for all the assets, ensuring the project's tools, methods, and collaborations have lasting impact. This has been and is still being created on the project's website. More specifically:
 - The GREEN Engine - <https://www.greengage-project.eu/green-engine/>
 - Documentation of various GREENGAGE tools and technologies - <https://greengage-project.github.io/Documentation/>
 - GREENGAGE Academy - <https://www.greengage-project.eu/academy/>, and
 - Knowledge Base - <https://www.greengage-project.eu/knowledge-base/>

4.1 Building Sustainable Stakeholder Network(s)

For building a sustainable stakeholder network we propose the following:

- Build a framework for forming long-term consortia involving:

- Public administration.
- Citizen observers.
- Local organizations.
- Create guidelines for maintaining communication channels post-project.

During its lifetime, GREENGAGE built the platform citizenobservers.eu which shall be the starting point for creating a stakeholder network for Citizen Observatories.

4.2 Publishing and Promoting GREENGAGE Training Assets

For publishing and promoting GREENGAGE training assets we propose the following:

- Create strategies for publishing and disseminating:
 - Use the created training materials, but also create new ones tailored for future Observatories.
 - Publish Observatory/experiment results via city portals and academic platforms.
- Use open access platforms to maximize visibility. GREENGAGE, e.g., published all its public deliverables on Zenodo. Here is the URL: <https://zenodo.org/communities/greengage/records>

4.3 Open Data Integration

For Open Data integration, GREENGAGE proposes the following:

- Ensure to link or copy (to Druid on the GREEN Engine) Open Government Data that is relevant to an Observatory, raising awareness for already existing data which citizens might not know of.
- Establish interfaces to integrate Citizen Observatory data into:
 - City open data portals.
 - GEOSS and similar platforms.

E.g. by linking GREENGAGE's Superset Dashboards into city run webpages.
- Try to adhere to best practices for ensuring data usability and accessibility, e.g., FAIR principles.

4.4 GREENGAGE Observers' Idea Exchange Platform (Discourse/Collaborative Environment)

To sustain and grow a Citizen Observer community, make use of GREENGAGE's idea exchange and discussion platforms ([Discourse](#) and [Collaborative Environment](#)). They can be used to develop and sustain an open platform for idea exchange. Important here are:

- Hosting and moderation guidelines.
- Features to facilitate collaboration and innovation.

4.5 GREEN Engine Tools and Documentation - Sustainability

GREENGAGE plans to have the **GREEN Engine tools and apps up and running for at least 4 years** after the lifetime of the project, hosted on AIT servers and on SushiDev premises (regarding the GREENGAGE App backend). To be sustainable, the project made sure that

- Open-Source tools (e.g., under the MIT open-source license) were widely used and combined with each other.
- Best practices for maintaining repositories (e.g., GitHub) have been established.
- Documentation guidelines were created and published on platforms which are publicly available, to ensure ease of use for new adopters.

- Packaging tools using easy to deploy approaches such as Docker containers.

4.6 Engaging Local Communities

For the engagement with local communities GREENGAGE proposes the following for future Observatories:

- Partner with local community organizations to continue using the GREEN Engine and the project's developed workflows.
- Find strategies for integrating GREENGAGE's assets into ongoing community activities.

4.7 SME Involvement and Business Plans for GREENGAGE Technologies and Workflows

Scaling to New Cities and Concepts: With the support of a partner to facilitate negotiations, the app can be tailored to the unique needs of additional cities. This includes reconfiguring the Citizen Observatory (CO) toolbox (i.e., the GREEN Engine) to accommodate diverse research frameworks beyond surveys and opinion scales. Expanding integrations to include more advanced air quality sensors, geodata collection tools, and citizen interaction apps can broaden its appeal and utility. Customizing the backend to suit specific municipal needs ensures that the app remains adaptable and relevant across diverse urban environments.

Full-Cycle Service Expansion via AI Solutions: In the future, by leveraging an internal multi-agent AI platform, GREENGAGE might offer municipalities a complete data processing and management solution. This would transform the app into a self-sustaining ecosystem, capable of handling the entire research cycle - from data collection through processing and interpretation. By offering this as an additional service, the GREENGAGE platform will become a robust and indispensable tool for municipalities, enabling informed decision-making and policy development based on actionable insights.

To sustain also the involvement of SMEs in the GREENGAGE tool development, GREENGAGE:

- supported the SMEs within the consortium to develop business plans for the project assets.
- explored commercialization opportunities while maintaining open access where appropriate.

In its commercial application, the GREENGAGE App might be marketed as a turnkey solution for municipalities, packaged as a "research and communication tool aimed at establishing a dialogue with citizens and collaboratively improving urban conditions." This comprehensive offering would include the app, backend support, training, and optional integration with advanced technologies such as AI-driven data processing.

Through collaboration in follow-up projects, the GREENGAGE App can then expand its scope and reach, while establishing itself as a standard tool for Citizen Observatories. By partnering with organizations and municipalities, it has the potential to become a widely recognized solution for improving urban well-being across Europe and beyond.

4.8 Validating replication and scaling

GREENGAGE has repeatedly demonstrated that its tools are both replicable and scalable across diverse geographical, cultural, and operational contexts. Throughout the project, several Citizen Observatories were successfully established and tested in multiple pilot locations. For example, observatories were implemented at DEUSTO in Bilbao (Spain), AIT in Vienna (Austria), and SSPCR in Bolzano (Italy), each validating the replication potential of the GREENGAGE framework and toolset under different local conditions.

Similarly, in Bristol and Turano, multiple observatories were created, each tailored to the needs and characteristics of a specific community group. These observatories tested the scalability of the GREENGAGE tools by applying them in contexts that varied significantly in terms of demographics and thematic focus. The consistent positive results across these sites highlight the flexibility of the GREENGAGE approach and confirm that the tools can be adapted, expanded, and sustained in a wide variety of settings.

Collectively, these deployments provide strong evidence that the GREENGAGE tools are mature, transferable, and robust enough to support both local-level implementation and broader regional or national scaling efforts.

5 Implementation Roadmap

The following steps have been undertaken to achieve short to long term sustainability of GREENGAGE assets:

- GREENGAGE assets were made accessible through different public repositories including Zenodo, GitHub and YouTube for wider adoption by various stakeholders.
- For replication, we are currently planning to use GREENGAGE in proposal to further Horizon Europe projects e.g., HORIZON-CL5-2026-01-D6-13: Safety of Cyclists, Pedestrians and Users of Micromobility Devices.
- For upscaling, GREENGAGE pilots will gain first-hand experience of using GREENGAGE assets. A continuous dialogue will take place with the pilot owners about sustaining the outcomes beyond the project lifetime. This would also require engagement with commercial partners and developing a business model to ensure no one is disadvantaged.
- Roles and responsibilities of key stakeholders are still being clarified. Policy makers as key stakeholders have to be included at an early point in the process to ensure both participation and a more fluent uptake. GREENGAGE COs provide data, but the uptake of this data is dependent on the quality, quantity, and the process of policy making. As such, the expectations of the policy makers have to be assuaged beforehand: what are they supposed to do with the data? This can range from complementing their existing datasets, to being confronted with an alternative. In addition, new information through analysis of the data e.g., to evaluate policies or planning interventions to serve specific indicators could play an important role. To ensure the involvement of policy makers in COs, the clear management, and the possible uptake of CO data, expectation management is a key activity during the process.
- One lesson learned by GREENGAGE is that it is essential that Citizen Science projects, such as those proposed by GREENGAGE, do not focus solely on urban areas but also include small rural areas. These regions, often overlooked in decision-making processes, present a unique set of challenges that require specific, targeted approaches. Small rural communities not only need tools to collect environmental data, but they must also be able to develop relevant open data that can feed into local decision-making and influence broader policies. In this context, it is important that local administrations, supported by initiatives like Citizen Observatories, learn to manage even the simplest data collection activities. This not only enhances their ability to monitor their environment but also allows them to participate meaningfully in a governance process that promotes sustainability. Small rural areas, in fact, can greatly benefit from creating accessible, shared data that addresses local needs, which can then be used to attract resources, improve services, and enhance community resilience during time, attracting stakeholder to generate answers to the territory needs. This provides an excellent opportunity to GREENGAGE to tap into the rural communities for building Citizen Observatories.

6 Further Recommendations and Conclusion

This document sets out a series of recommendations to support the effective replication, scaling, and long-term sustainability of GREENGAGE tools. Several strategic pathways are being identified, including outreach to additional cities, exploration of commercial opportunities, development of public-private partnerships, research funding grant applications, activation of new use cases emerging from existing

GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories, and improved packaging and ease of deployment of GREENGAGE assets.

To maximise the impact and reach of GREENGAGE, the following recommendations are proposed:

Prioritise Actions for Replication and Sustainability: Focus resources on the most promising replication opportunities, building on demonstrated successes from pilot cities. Establish a clear roadmap for continued use of GREENGAGE tools beyond the project timeline.

Provide Tailored Support to Cities with Different Capacities: Cities vary widely in terms of technical maturity, staff capacity, governance structures, and community engagement experience. GREENGAGE tools should therefore be accompanied by customised guidance and adaptable implementation models that can meet cities where they are.

Identify Key Risks and Define Mitigation Strategies: Upscaling requires awareness of operational, technical, financial, and organisational risks. Proactive planning—including risk assessment, mitigation measures, and sustainability planning—will support smoother replication and long-term stability.

The evidence gathered throughout the project demonstrates that the GREENGAGE tools are mature, adaptable, and suitable for wider deployment. By prioritising sustainability, offering tailored support, and managing risks effectively, GREENGAGE can continue to expand its impact and enable more cities and communities to benefit from citizen-driven environmental intelligence.